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PROBLEMS OF DIGITALIZATION AND PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATION IN THE FIELD OF MORAL EDUCATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: The modern world is experiencing a period of rapid digital change, deeply affecting all aspects of life, including education. Information and communication technology, artificial intelligence, online platforms, and interactive tools are actively transforming traditional teaching methods, creating a new educational environment for the young generation. In these conditions, the moral education of young schoolchildren takes on special importance, because this age is the foundation for forming worldviews, values and social norms.

The relevance of this study is emphasized by the need to understand how digital innovations influence the process of moral development of elementary school students. On the one hand, modern educational technologies broaden access to knowledge, stimulate cognitive interest, and enable individualization of learning. On the other hand, digital transformation is creating new challenges: a lack of preparedness among educators to work with new technologies, Reduced personal communication between participants in the educational process and the potential negative impact of excessive use of gadgets on children's emotional and moral development.

Key words: digital transformation, innovative education, information and communication technologies, moral education, elementary school students, digital learning environment, pedagogical innovation, educational policy of Uzbekistan.

INTRODUCTION

The reality today is that, every day, there are massive digital changes taking place worldwide, affecting many spheres of activity, including education. Based on this, these changes have an impact on innovations in the field of pedagogy that affect moral education of young schoolchildren. Modernized teaching methods not only improve the quality and level of education, but also create problems for previously non-existent ones.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 OP-5538 "On additional measures to improve the system of management of public education" one of the main tasks is: implementation of modern information communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of public education, which is today the leading task of the modern educational system. Moral education plays a key role in educating and improving our societies, particularly in the age of digital innovation. The subjects taught, particularly those related to the moral education of young schoolchildren, highlight and emphasize the importance of eradicating digital innovation problems.

Today, there are many challenges with the use of digital innovations in pedagogy related to the adaptation and implementation of these ideas. The concept of "digital technology" itself was widely used in production and not previously in teaching. After its approval and direct introduction into the field of teaching, learners faced the problem of changing the very essence of the educational process.

Another, no less important issue that is widely discussed around the world is proper training for educators in using digital innovations. The introduction of Internet teaching, artificial intelligence, VR and AR technologies entails not only qualification but also psychological training for more comfortable and widespread use of digitalization in the teaching system. It should be mentioned that pedagogical innovations must fit into the state curriculum of education and moral upbringing of lower classes. Among other things, the digitization process often begins spontaneously, without taking into account the experience, readiness, and knowledge of the teacher. Also, it can often cause wariness, distrust, disorientation, and reduce motivation to implement anything new related to technology. It is necessary to introduce training programmes for teachers and students on the use of various programmes, to prepare instructions on the use of electronic libraries and the ability to separate and analyse information received, because the same information can have different content or be unreliable.

It is also important to take into account the age of lower-school students, as excessive use of digital technology can have a detrimental impact on their psychological and emotional health. While the original goal was to improve moral education of schoolchildren through pedagogical innovations. Another likely problem is a dearth of lively communication, which in turn reduces empathy, impairs the development of communication skills, and can hinder improvements in the system for teaching spirituality to lower classes.

The main focus of this study is to understand how digital innovations affect the process of moral formation in young school children. The aim is also to identify which pedagogical approaches contribute to the successful introduction of modern digital tools in the educational environment of primary school.

Analysis of scientific literature, legal and regulatory documents and pedagogical research on the topic of digitalization of education and moral education. A study found that digital innovations have significant educational potential to develop the moral qualities of primary school students. The use of interactive learning platforms, multimedia materials and electronic learning resources stimulates students' interest in learning, enhances their ability to think critically, and promotes social values.

However, along with the positive aspects, digitalization of education has its challenges. These include a lack of teachers' skills in applying the latest technologies, reduced direct communication between children, the risk of information overload, and the potential harm of excessive gadget hobbies to children's emotional states.

Conclusion: The digitalization of education is a natural and logical stage in the evolution of the existing educational system. The introduction of digital technology offers new ways to improve teaching and the quality of moral education in the lower grades. However, the success of these innovations is directly due to a competent methodical approach to the organization of the educational process.

The results of this work show that the use of digital tools requires a systematic and scientifically sound approach. This approach should aim not only at the transmission of academic knowledge, but also at educating students in spiritual and moral orientation. The key to successful adoption of digital innovation is training the teaching staff, developing students' digital literacy and maintaining genuine personal communication within the educational process.

Areas for future scientific research include the development of concrete methods to integrate digital developments into the process of moral education of young schoolchildren, as well as the development of practical guides for primary-school teachers.

REFERENCES:

1. Cross J. An informal history of eLearning. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/240601967_An_informal_history_of_eLearning (accessed: 20.04.2020).
2. Shityakova N.P., Verkhovykh I.V., Zabrodina I.V. (2020) Studying the attitude of teachers to the possibilities and risks of spiritual and moral education in the context of digitalization. Prospects for science and education, 2020, no. 6 (48), pp. 446-458. (In Russian).

3. Cross J. An informal history of eLearning. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/240601967_An_informal_history_of_eLearning

4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 6, 2020 No. PP-4851